

ABOUT THE TYPES OF POTTERY VESSELS MADE IN OTHER THAN METAL VESSELS IN THE IX-XII CENTURIES OF OLD TERMEZ

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Abstract. *The role of material culture samples in studying the history of our country is incomparable. Because the examples of material culture help us to study the history of our people in the most ancient period when there was no writing yet. The fact that every historical monument in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is under state protection is a respect for our history and past. As long as there is a historical object, it certainly contains the past, yesterday's work and work of our people.*

Keywords: *historical object, Termiz, Karatepa, Fayoztepa.*

Introduction. The role of material culture samples in studying the history of our country is incomparable. Because the examples of material culture help us to study the history of our people in the most ancient period when there was no writing yet. The fact that every historical monument in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is under state protection is a respect for our history and past. As long as there is a historical object, it certainly contains the past, yesterday's work and work of our people [1].

The history of pottery in Termez was not specifically studied until recently. Because the scientists who conducted archaeological work in Termiz focused more on the study of unique monuments such as the Palace of Governors of Termiz, Karatepa, Fayoztepa. However, in the mid-thirties of the last century, professor M.E. Masson noted the presence of potters' quarters of different centuries in several places of Termez. Since ancient times, each region has had its own school of pottery making. When cooking ceramic dishes, the hearth is usually dug into the ground in the khumdans. The top of the ceramic cooking room was dome-shaped. There was a special hole in the middle or at one end of the dome, through which ceramic dishes were placed in the khumdan for cooking and ready-made dishes were taken. During the cooking process, these holes are closed. In order to cook ceramics well, it is necessary to have a temperature of 800-900 degrees [2,3].

In the area of Old Termiz, many finds from the Middle Ages have been found and studied by many historians and archaeologists. Let's talk about ceramic dishes of Termiz, made in imitation of unique metal dishes. Based on our research, in the Middle Ages, the production of glazed and unglazed pottery was at a high level in Chaganyon and Termiz regions. Ceramics are distinguished by a variety of assortments, high technological aspects, richness and complexity of decorative patterns and compositions. It follows the traditions developed in other medieval pottery centers and at the same time has a number of local differences, which allows us to raise the question of its existence at the time it was developed. In the Middle Ages, the pottery school of Termiz was formed[4].

Hoshimgird or Hashimjird, the second largest city in Termiz province, is also a day's journey away from Termiz. Hashimgird is not mentioned in XI-XII centuries.

There are different opinions about her husband. M.E. Masson assumed that it was located in the Navshahar region, O.G. Bolshakov in the vicinity of Sherabad, and E.V. Rtveladze assumed that it was near the village of Kaptarkhana near Angor. According to Shamsiddin Kamoliddinov, this place is located near the city of Sherabad, on the banks of the river flowing from the Sherabad mountains [5].

Literature review. In the course of the research work, among the ceramic vessels of the IX-XII centuries, ceramic vessels made in imitation of metal vessels are more common. As an example, we can see in the example of the objects stored in the Archaeological Museum of Termez today. Most of these findings are kept in the Termez Archeological Museum, the only one specialized in the field of archeology in our country, and are displayed in exhibition halls. If we dwell on some of these findings, on June 15, 2022, unique historical findings were accidentally found during road construction in the city of Termez (coordinates: 37.2539361,67.3056543). These ancient finds are 2 medieval jugs. These findings were discovered by the workers of the Surkhandarya Region bridge use facility: Sh.Karimov and A.Matievlar and reported to the Termez Archaeological Museum. In response to the appeal, R. Khudoyberdiev, deputy director for scientific affairs of the Termez Archaeological Museum, and deputy director for general issues. The Charievs went to the scene and took the exhibits to the museum fund. The surface of the ceramic jugs is skillfully decorated with various decorative reliefs.

Research Methodology. In order to study the naming of these vessels, which are common in medieval monuments, a series of literature analyzes on medieval pottery was carried out. As a result, 4 monographs and articles studied the naming of this type of vessels and formed a list of them. Also, on the basis of the literature devoted to the research of archaeological pottery, the laws of naming ceramic vessels were studied.

Analysis and results. The priceless finds are currently being repaired in the museum's restoration department. KP 37125 Kozacha. The jug was made on the pottery wheel and baked in the oven. XI-XII centuries. Size: 16x6.5 cm. Unique ceramics of Termez are made in imitation of metal vessels. Another important aspect of the vessel is made of Amudarya clay oil. About the structure of the vessel, the part from the belly to the base of the vessel has been preserved. The neck and flange are not preserved. Also, the vessel is decorated with vertical relief patterns on the belly and similar vertical relief patterns on the lower part. Each pattern is separated by circular rings.

KP 3525. Pitcher. IX-XII centuries. Size: 15.5x6.3 cm. The jug was made in a pottery kiln and baked in a kiln. This jug is also made in imitation of metal containers. Another important aspect of the vessel is made of Amudarya clay oil. About the structure of the vessel, the part from the belly to the base of the vessel has been preserved. The neck and flange are not preserved. Also, some parts of the junction of the neck part and the reservoir part have been preserved. In this part, the relief is decorated with vertical oblique lines. Then two circular lines are made in the lower part of this ornament. The belly of the vessel is decorated with circular leaves and carved flowers in relief. The jug is made narrower from the belly to the base. The tag is flat disc-shaped.

KP 3525-2. A jug with a branch. IX-XII centuries. Size: 21x9 cm. The jug was made in a pottery kiln and baked in a kiln. This jug is also made in imitation of metal containers. Another important aspect of the vessel is made of Amudarya clay oil. About the structure of the vessel, the

part from the neck to the base of the vessel has been preserved. Part of the flange is preserved. Also, the part of the trunk attached to the body of the vessel has been preserved. This part is decorated with carved lines. Then two circular embossed lines are made in the lower part of this decoration. The belly of the vessel is decorated with carved geometric patterns with carved flowers. The jug is made narrower from the belly to the base. The tag is flat disc-shaped.

KP 3525-3. Jug. IX-XII centuries. Size: 12.5x6.6 cm. The jug was made in a pottery kiln and baked in a kiln. This jug is also made in imitation of metal containers. Another important aspect of the vessel is made of Amudarya clay oil. About the structure of the vessel, the part from the belly to the base of the vessel has been preserved. The neck and flange are not preserved. Also, some parts of the junction of the neck part and the reservoir part have been preserved. In this part, the engraving is decorated with different vertical lines. Then two circular lines are made in the lower part of this ornament. The belly of the vessel is decorated with flowers in different geometrical shapes. The jug is made narrower from the belly to the base. The tag is flat disc-shaped.

Exhibits of the Archaeological Museum of Termiz

INV	The material of the item	The name of the element	Period	Size	A photo of the item	Similar metal products	Drawing of the object
37125	Ceramic	Pitcher	IX-XII centuries Old Termiz	16x6.5			
3525-1	Ceramic	Pitcher	IX-XII centuries Old Termiz	h-15,5 dg-6,3			
3525-2	Ceramic	Pitcher	IX-XII centuries Old Termiz	h-21 dg-9			
3525-3	Ceramic	Pitcher	IX-XII centuries Old Termiz	h-12,5 dg-6,6			

On June 15, 2022, in the city of Termiz (coordinates: 37.2539361, 67.3056543), 2 unique pots were randomly found during road construction.

INV 3525-2. pitcher IX-XII centuries. A.D

INV 37125. pitcher IX-XII centuries. A.D

INV 3525-1. pitcher IX-XII centuries. A.D

INV 3525-3. pitcher IX-XII centuries. A.D

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